

Unlocking Forensic Potential: CODIS Implementation and DNA Data Exchange in Romania

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Abstract

In late February 2024, the Romanian National System of Judicial Genetic Data (NSJGD) achieved a significant milestone, surpassing 100,000 DNA profiles in CODIS. This accomplishment calls for celebration and offers an opportune moment to reflect on the invaluable role CODIS plays as a forensic tool. The utilization of CODIS in Romania extends beyond national DNA searching to encompass automated international DNA searching, pedigree searching and familial DNA searching, demonstrating its versatility in addressing diverse investigative scenarios. This article provides an in-depth exploration of CODIS, focusing primarily on its implementation in Romania at the national level.

Keywords: DNA database, Combined DNA Index System (CODIS), National System of Judicial Genetic Data (NSJGD), STR, Y-STR, automated DNA data exchange, Forensic Genetics, Romania.

1. Introduction

Combined DNA Index System (CODIS) holds significance on two fronts: firstly, as the national DNA database of the United States of America, curated and managed by the Federal Bureau of Investigation (FBI). Secondly, it denotes the database management system of DNA profiles from convicted offenders, unresolved crime scene evidence and missing persons, spanning administrative tiers ranging from local to state and national levels.

From an organizational standpoint, the first meaning, in Romania aligns with the Genetic Profiles Database, an integral component of the National System of Judicial Genetic Data [1].

For the purpose of this article, our focus will primarily delve into the second connotation of "CODIS" and its strategic deployment within Romania.

In the past, particularly in conjunction with the "standard set" terms, CODIS was referred to as the 13 or 20 standard STR set, utilized by CODIS database management systems. However, this terminology has become obsolete due to advancements in PCR kit manufacturing, which are further elaborated upon in a separate section (3. STR standard set).

The development of the national DNA database of the United States by the FBI commenced in 1998. Presently, CODIS is deployed across 203 federal, state, and local participating laboratories, encompassing all 50 states, the District of Columbia, Puerto Rico, federal law enforcement agencies, and the Department of Defense. Internationally, the CODIS database management system is utilized by over 58 countries for their own law enforcement purposes. It's important to note that these CODIS installations operate independently and do not directly link with the USA national DNA database [2]. Theoretically, another country could establish a connection with the USA national database through bilateral agreements [3] and following specific search rules (e.g. Prüm-like rules).

While such agreements are operational in fields like fingerprints, they have not been implemented in the DNA domain yet, primarily due to legal considerations that require resolution at the national level within the USA.

We prefer to conceptualize CODIS not merely as a "computer software program," but rather as a comprehensive

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database management system. In contemporary terms, it has evolved into a server-client platform equipped with forensic tool functionalities and an array of server-side features intricately tied to Windows Servers and Windows SQL Servers. These encompass crucial aspects such as security, communication protocols, resource management, and scalability, among others.

The forensic tools integrated within CODIS are accessible from the client-side and are organized into modules, each tailored to fulfill specific tasks. These encompass a diverse range of functionalities including communication tools, statistical analysis capabilities, DNA profile management utilities, pedigree management features, report generation functionalities, various types of searches, as well as tools for managing matches and rankings, and much more.

DNA profiles within CODIS are organized into indexes and categories, which can be easily configured to facilitate specific comparisons among DNA profile groups while adhering to national and international legislation governing this field. In the Romanian CODIS installation, which now operates only at the national level, the DNA profiles are structured into distinct categories as follows: Convicted Offenders (82.9%), Suspects (6.2%), Forensic Unknown (3.1%), Forensic Mixtures (0.4%), Unidentified Persons (0.2%), Eliminations and Victims (0.4%), Missing Persons (0.1%), Relatives (0.4%), International Requests (6.3%) and other (0.1%).

This categorization ensures efficient management and retrieval of DNA profiles, enabling precise analysis and comparison as per the requirements of forensic investigations while maintaining compliance with pertinent legal frameworks.

2. Legislation background

The initial steps toward establishing a national DNA database in Romania took shape in 2003 with the signing of a protocol between the General Inspectorate of the Romanian Police under the Ministry of Administration and Interior, and the National Prison Administration under the Ministry of Justice. This protocol paved the way for the collection of DNA samples from convicted offenders, mirroring the procedures established in the field of dactyloscopy and the existing Automated Fingerprint Identification System (AFIS) already in operation within Romania at that time.

Subsequently, this protocol served as the foundation for the enactment of a comprehensive law in 2008, delineating the organization and operation of the National Judicial Genetic Data System [1]. The methodological norms governing the implementation of this law were finalized after an additional three-year period [4]. Over time, the law underwent numerous minor amendments and two significant updates, as a consequence of the establishment of the National Register of Sexual Crimes [5] and the National Register of Drug Trafficking-related Crimes [6].

In terms of DNA data exchange through traditional channels, Romania actively participates as a member of key international police cooperation agencies such as Interpol and Europol [7, 8]. These organizations serve as crucial platforms facilitating the exchange of various forensic data among national agencies, including DNA profiles. Through their

technical frameworks, Interpol and Europol enable seamless collaboration and information sharing, enhancing the effectiveness of law enforcement efforts on a global scale.

Concerning the automated DNA data exchange, Romania has taken significant steps to expedite this process by signing various international agreements. Among these agreements is the Prüm Treaty, which subsequently evolved into two Council of the European Union decisions (JHA 615 and 616), now mandatory for all EU member states [9, 10]. Additionally, Romania has entered into agreements with the United States [3] and the Balkan countries under the Police Cooperation Convention for Southeast Europe (PCC SEE) [11]. These agreements empower Romania to engage in automated DNA data exchange with the United States, European Union member states, and six Balkan countries.

Romania's membership in these agencies and by leveraging these partnerships and frameworks, underscores its commitment to international cooperation in combating crime across borders and ensuring the swift exchange of vital forensic information for investigative purposes.

3. STR standard set

To ensure global coherence in the Forensic Genetics field, three pivotal STR standard sets have emerged over the years: the CODIS STR core, European Standard Set (ESS), and Interpol Standard Set of Loci (ISSOL), each with its distinct background and evolution. With Romania's accession to the EU in 2004, it adopted the ESS, which underwent a significant upgrade in 2009, incorporating five additional STR markers [12].

However, the proliferation of PCR amplification kits by major manufacturers now mitigates any discrepancies between these standards. These kits encompass all autosomal STR markers specified in the aforementioned standards (21 autosomal STR markers and Amelogenin). Consequently, Romania, like many other countries, utilizes all available autosomal STR markers present in commercial kits.

Furthermore, modern versions of CODIS exhibit flexibility in accommodating additional autosomal STR loci. Additionally, CODIS has the capability to import and conduct local searches for Y chromosome STRs and mitochondrial DNA SNPs. In addition to autosomal STR markers utilized with past and current PCR amplification kits (such as SGM plus, Identifiler, ESSplex, ESSplex SE, GlobalFiler, GlobalFiler Express, Investigator 24plex QS, and Investigator 24plex GO!), Romania incorporates Y chromosome STRs into CODIS using PCR amplification kits like Yfiler, Argus Y12, and Argus Y28.

4. Romanian CODIS related history

During the period spanning from 2003 to 2012, the landscape for managing forensic DNA databases was characterized by a scarcity of software options in the market. The available solutions either entailed exorbitant costs or necessitated the development of bespoke, in-house software solutions. This last approach was observed in various countries such as Austria, Germany, and the UK.

No.	Marker	CODIS	ESS	ISSOL
1.	CSF1PO	x		
2.	FGA	x	X	x
3.	TH01	x	X	x
4.	TPOX	x		
5.	VWA	x	X	x
6.	D3S1358	x	X	x
7.	D5S818	x		
8.	D7S820	x		
9.	D8S1179	x	X	x
10.	D13S317	x		
11.	D16S539	x	[x]	
12.	D18S51	x	x	x
13.	D21S11	x	x	x
14.	Amelogenin	x	[x]	#
15.	D2S441	[x]	x	
16.	D2S1338	[x]	[x]	
17.	D10S1248	[x]	x	
18.	D12S391	[x]	x	
19.	D19S433	[x]	[x]	
20.	D22S1045	[x]	x	
21.	D1S1656		x	
22.	SE33		[x]	

Table 1 – DNA STR standards (CODIS STR markers x - in 1997-2017 period, [x] - after 2017, ESS STR markers x - in 2001-2009 period, [x] - after 2009, # - optional)

Consequently, organizations faced an important decision between procuring existing software or allocating resources towards cultivating internal expertise, typically through IT developer teams. Romania navigated both avenues: opting for purchased software solutions like Dimensions v1.0 and v2.0, while concurrently embarking on the development of proprietary systems. Notably, the latter approach involved the integration of three Prüm tools – a Matching Engine from Austria, a Communication Tool from Germany, and a Graphical User Interface (GUI) from the Netherlands – within a virtual machine environment [13].

Each of these strategies boasted distinct advantages and drawbacks. However, the ultimate outcome – whether deemed successful or unsuccessful – hinged on adept contextual understanding and efficient resource management.

Before embracing the functionalities offered by the Prüm tools, CODIS had undergone six software iterations. This transition marked a significant milestone, particularly for European Union countries seeking a reliable, expeditious, and cost-effective software solution to comply with the mandatory Council decisions JHA 615 and 616 [9,10]. These decisions mandated the implementation of automated DNA data exchange within the framework of the European Union.

In 2011, the FBI introduced CODIS v7.0 to Europe, a pivotal development embraced by Romania among other countries. This adoption facilitated the management of

Romania's national DNA database (NSJGD), while streamlining automated DNA data exchange with fellow EU countries. Over the years Romania updated its CODIS to versions 8 and 9.

FBI bypassed the 10th version of CODIS due to significant code alterations. In 2024, the 12th version is rolled out in the USA and in parallel 11th version, at international level. Romania is poised to transition 11th version in due course, likely following suit with other pioneering European countries. Drawing from past experiences, it's prudent to await the resolution of initial bugs before undergoing substantial updates. Thus, Romania aims to maintain full operational capacity until any teething issues are addressed by the FBI, ensuring a smooth transition to the new version.

5. DNA data exchange

The search workflow operates through three distinct levels of scrutiny. Initially, before DNA profiles are uploaded into CODIS, a preliminary comparison occurs. This entails matching unknown DNA profiles from criminal cases against those of a pool of suspects. In this stage also enters comparisons of the relatives of missing persons and unidentified human remains, aiming to establish kinship connections.

If this initial comparison yields no matches, the process advances to a second level conducted at the national level. Here, the unknown DNA profiles are uploaded into CODIS for further investigation and comparison. In the event of another negative outcome, the search proceeds to a third level.

At this juncture, the search expands to a European scale in an automated way. Alternatively, non-automated searches can be conducted globally through collaboration with international law enforcement agencies such as Europol and Interpol. This comprehensive approach ensures exhaustive efforts are made to resolve criminal cases and establish crucial connections on a global scale.

Under ideal circumstances, the third automated search, commonly referred to as a Prüm search, typically takes approximately 15 minutes. This process, governed by the Council decisions JHA 615 and 616 [9,10], involves the transmission of a Romanian DNA profile to all EU member states engaged in DNA data exchange with Romania. Subsequently, the profile is searched within the respective national DNA databases, culminating in a swift determination of either a HIT or no-HIT outcome, also known as the “Prüm I first step”.

Upon receiving a HIT response, Romania has the prerogative to request additional data pertaining to the profile that generated the match. This can include personal information or case-related data, constituting the “Prüm I second step”. This streamlined protocol ensures efficient collaboration and information sharing among EU member states, facilitating the resolution of criminal cases and the exchange of critical insights.

Presently, Romania has established automated DNA data exchange with 25 European countries, fostering seamless collaboration and information sharing across borders. These countries include: Austria, Belgium, Bulgaria, Croatia, Cyprus, Czech Republic, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Luxembourg,

Malta, Netherlands, Poland, Portugal, Slovakia, Slovenia, Spain, Sweden and United Kingdom (Fig. 1). With Italy the testing phase was initiated in December 2023.

Additionally, Romania actively extends its assistance to Police Cooperation Convention for Southeast Europe (PCC SEE) member states, contributing to the operationalization of automated DNA data exchange in the Balkans. These member states encompass: Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Moldova, Montenegro, North Macedonia and Serbia [10].

Figure 1 – Romania automated DNA data exchange status – April 2024 (yellow – countries operational with Romania, blue – countries not yet operational with Romania, grey – other countries)

This collaborative effort underscores Romania's commitment to enhancing regional cooperation and bolstering the efficacy of DNA data exchange initiatives across Europe.

Highlighting the significance of this forensic tool, it's noteworthy that 47.47% of technical matches originate at national level, while 52.53% stem from automated DNA data exchange. Furthermore, when considering reported matches, 27.19% are derived from national matches, whereas an overwhelming 72.81% are reported matches resulting from automated DNA data exchange. This underscores the important role played by international collaboration in maximizing the effectiveness of forensic endeavors.

6. Direct Searching vs Pedigree Searching

Within CODIS, two primary methods of search and comparison exist: direct searching, conducted under the *one-to-many* rule, and indirect searching, known as pedigree searching, conducted under the *many-to-many* rule.

In direct searching, the objective is to identify the source of an unknown forensic DNA profile. This method typically yields a direct match (HIT) between one or more DNA profiles, aiding in the identification of a person.

On the other hand, pedigree searching, or indirect searching, operates under the *many-to-many* rule. Rather than seeking direct matches, this method generates lists of candidate DNA profiles (ranks). Pedigree searching is specifically tailored to locate missing persons and unidentified remains. It achieves this by comparing DNA profiles from these categories with those of their relatives within a pedigree tree. This approach is instrumental in facilitating the resolution of cases involving missing persons and unidentified human remains, leveraging kinship connections to establish human identity.

At 100.000 DNA profiles in Romanian CODIS there were 987 pedigree trees (741 built with international DNA profiles and 246 built with national DNA profiles) which generated 3561 ranks (candidate profiles). That sums up an average ratio of 3,6 ranks per pedigree tree.

7. The Familial DNA Searching

Familial DNA Searching involves seeking potential relatives of an unidentified DNA profile within a national DNA database. This method can be viewed as a hybrid approach, combining elements of both Direct and Pedigree searches. Its outcomes typically yield candidate lists, necessitating further investigation by criminal investigators.

It is essential to note that Familial DNA Searching is ideally employed in cold criminal cases, where conventional investigative methods have been exhausted. This method should be approached with care and discretion, ensuring adherence to ethical guidelines and legal frameworks [15].

During the 11th European CODIS User Conference held in Copenhagen, Denmark on April 28, 2015, Mathilde Huet from Police Technique et Scientifique, Direction Centrale de la Police Judiciaire delivered a presentation titled "Resolution of a criminal case with familial searching in CODIS", highlighting the famous French Elodie case [16]. Following this event, this success story was disseminated across various training sessions for criminal investigators in Romania.

As a direct result of this dissemination effort, the first request for a familial DNA search of a cold case was initiated in Romania in August 2019. One year later, Romania achieved a significant milestone when it successfully solved its first homicide case utilizing this method [17].

8. The efficiency

Out of 100,000 profiles obtained, a total of 55819 technical matches were identified by CODIS using default search rules at national and international levels. From these matches, 4332 were further evaluated by experts and specialists, and subsequently reported to criminal investigators. This translates to a general ratio of approximately 1 reported match for every 12.9 technical matches, 1 technical match for every 1.8 DNA profiles, and 1 reported match for every 23 DNA profiles. These parameter values serve as indicators of CODIS efficiency and monitoring them annually provides insights into CODIS performance over time.

Although these parameter values are significant, it's essential to underscore that the primary beneficiaries of the NSJGD are the EU member states. This assertion stems from

the fact that 89.9% of DNA profiles within CODIS belong to persons and the majority (82.9%) are Convicted Offenders.

However, due to the way judicial system is organized in Romania, feedback on the final outcomes of reported matches is not provided. Consequently, the impact of reported matches remains unknown. Nevertheless, occasional feedback from the mass-media, in significant criminal cases, indicates that some reported matches have played a crucial role in investigations [17].

A DNA database comprising 100,000 profiles may be considered relatively small, especially considering the time frame, geographical scope, population dimension, and budgetary constraints of Romania. Nonetheless, it reflects a commendable effort given the resources available.

For comparison, the United Kingdom maintains approximately 7 million DNA profiles in its national DNA database [18]. Similarly, the United States boasts a database of 24 million DNA profiles [19], while China, the world's second populous country after India [20], possesses an estimated 80 million DNA profiles in its national DNA database [21].

These figures underscore the varying scales of forensic DNA databases globally, influenced by factors such as population size, technological advancements, and government initiatives.

Despite Romania's database being comparatively smaller, its efforts in DNA profiling contribute significantly to forensic investigations and criminal justice outcomes within its jurisdiction.

The progression of Romania's National DNA Database (NSJGD) is indeed noteworthy (Fig. 2). Starting from zero DNA profiles in 2003, it reached significant milestones, including 1,000 profiles in 2007, 10,000 profiles in 2009, and finally, 100,000 DNA profiles in 2024. Extrapolating this growth rate, it's projected that the NSJGD will reach the next milestone of 1 million DNA profiles in 2187 – 2192 period (the value varies depending on the calculation method used for estimation).

With the construction of five new small laboratories in Iași, Constanța, Timișoara, and Cluj, which commenced in 2023, alongside advancements in technology and the anticipated drop in sample analysis costs, it's plausible that the 1 million milestone will be achieved much sooner, possibly around the year 2080. This accelerated timeline suggests that future generations will witness the culmination of this significant achievement, after the current architects of the NSJGD and authors of this article have passed away.

However, attaining a milestone of 1 million may present challenges considering Romania's declining population. Moreover, given that CODIS (also NSJGP) is a forensic DNA database, reaching a 5% coverage of the current Romanian population raises legitimate concerns about the possible criminal activity in a such scenario.

9. Conclusions

Despite Romania's progress in expanding its DNA database to 100,000 profiles, challenges persist, including resource constraints and legislative considerations. Moving forward, it is essential to prioritize sustained investments in

human resources, infrastructure, and technology. These investments, coupled with strategic collaborations both domestically and internationally, are imperative to further enhance Romania's forensic capabilities and ensure the continued efficacy of CODIS in criminal justice endeavors.

By addressing these challenges head-on and fostering a culture of innovation and collaboration, Romania can continue to strengthen its position as a trustworthy member in Forensic Genetics field and contribute significantly to global efforts in crime prevention and justice.

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Figure 2 – NSIGD and CODIS timeline evolution (red squares = 0, 1000, 10.000 and 100.000 DNA profiles milestones)

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